

Seven New NOIRLab Survey Programs

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NSF's NOIRLab supports proposals for large observational surveys in addition to the standard telescope proposals awarded for single semesters at a time. Surveys are defined as programs that require large uniform datasets to answer important scientific questions and, crucially, that can support leading-edge archival research beyond the science goals of the original proposers. In return for the large allocation of resources, the proposers are required to return high-level data products to NOIRLab. These data products are made available for community use through services provided by the Community Science and Data Center.

The opportunity to propose new surveys is typically offered yearly, dependent on the resources available to support new programs. In our most recent call, we offered time on the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope and SOAR Telescope for programs to begin in the 2023B semester. We received 21 survey proposals, which were evaluated by a survey TAC panel selected specifically for this call, based on the preliminary letters of intent that we received in advance of the proposal deadline. Five proposals primarily using Blanco/DECam and two proposals primarily using SOAR were recommended and will be scheduled as follows:

GW-MMADS: Gravitational Wave Multi-Messenger Astronomy DECam Survey: This survey plans to use “target-of-opportunity” observations to characterize kilonovae and merging black hole systems identified as counterparts to gravitational wave events.

The DECam MAGIC Survey: Mapping the Ancient Galaxy in CaHK: This is a 54-night survey to chemically map 5500 square degrees of the Milky Way and its structures (e.g., the LMC, SMC, Sagittarius stream, and ultra-faint dwarfs) using the new narrow-band CaHK filter on DECam. This will enable broad, high-impact galactic archaeology studies connected to the first stars, early galactic evolution, and the formation of the Milky Way and the Magellanic Clouds.

CIDER: Charting Ionization During the Epoch of Reionization: CIDER was awarded 45 nights to do narrow-band imaging of a 12-square-degree field, using DECam. The goal is to identify hundreds of Lyman alpha galaxies and thus determine the IGM neutral fraction at redshift $z = 7.3$.

Efficiently Mapping the $z > 2$ Universe with Medium-Band Filters: This program will use 90 nights of DECam medium-band imaging survey over a 1000-square-degree area to provide an object catalog that will enable a detailed study of the $z > 2$ universe using DESI spectroscopy. Imaging this footprint with three new, medium-band filters spanning 4224–5036 Å will allow selection of 0.5 million $2.4 < z < 3.2$ Lyman Break Galaxies (LBGs) and 1.6 million Lyman-Alpha Emitters (LAEs).

Survey for Potentially Hazardous Small Aphelion NEOs Using DECam: DECam will be used near twilight to find small aphelion Near-Earth Objects (SA-NEOs) inside the Earth's orbit. This population of potentially hazardous objects (PHOs) is difficult for more standard opposition surveys to detect because they spend most of their time in daylight and are seen only when they fortuitously cross the Earth's orbit into the view of an opposition survey. The total twilight time used will be equivalent to six full nights.

SOARly Needed Spectra of Southern VLBI Sources: This survey will use nine nights on the Goodman spectrograph to determine AGN spectral types for a complete sample of radio sources detected with very long baseline interferometry (VLBI) observations at $\text{dec} < -30$, where there is currently a dearth of VLBI sources due to fewer baselines and VLBI observing sessions.

A Near-Infrared Spectral Extension to the MaStar Optical Spectral Stellar Library: The program will use TripleSpec for 42 nights on SOAR. Spectra with $R=3500$, over the 0.8–2.47 μm wavelength range, will be used to extend the continuous spectral library coverage for 600+ prime stars from the SDSS-IV MaNGA Stellar Library (MaStar; [Yan et al. 2019](#)), to 0.36–2.47 μm , with good flux calibration.